

RESILIENT SLIP FRICTION JOINT FOR STEEL MOMENT RESISTING BRACED FRAME**K Raghu**

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Abstract:

Recent studies shows that major earthquakes has end up in the severe damage of the structure, which led engineers in find of techniques which not only provide people's safety, but also aspire to cut-down damages in the structures. In this article, a single bay, ten-story concentric braced frame with non-buckling bracing is developed to study the energy dissipation. Particularly this evaluation is done to check their stability after earthquake loadings. Traditional lateral force resisting systems include moment resistant frames and frames that are concentrically braced. This Traditional lateral force resisting systems is in use for long period of time, but the result obtained from these methods is average level. The insufficient stiffness of moment-resisting frames and the inadequate ductility of concentrically braced frames have propelled significant research efforts toward the advancement of novel lateral resisting systems that include more stable hysteretic behavior, suitable ductility, control of damage, and energy dissipation capability. Conventional Moment Resisting Frames (MRFs) become softer and as a result energy dissipates in higher amount under seismic design analysis. There is a linked damage in important areas of the key structural members as a result of the earlier complaints. This collision could cause serious damage and long-lasting tremor following the earthquake. To prevent the drift, a self-centering damage evasion initiative known as Resilient Slip Friction Joint (RSFJ) was created for steel Moment resisting Frame. The RSFJ achieves both the behavior of self centering and the task of energy dissipation, there-by resulting in seismic resistance. Added to that, an innovative energy dissipater, present inside the RSFJ as the central fuse, supports the building. Self-centering friction-dampening brace members, as opposed to conventional brace members, make the greatest use of the available characteristics in steel structures with concentrically braced frames. This results in minimising residual deformation and withstand earthquake load without replacing any of the member. The present research compares the performance of moment-resisting braced frames with and without RSFJ dampers during seismic activity. The purpose of this research is to determine whether RSFJ dampers for steel moment resisting brace systems are a good replacement for the current standard bracing systems with dampers and give performance advantages.

Keywords: Resilient Slip Friction Joint, Dampers, Moment resisting braced frames, Earthquake, performance based design.

1. Introduction:

The Structural Engineer's line of business is to make sure of public conviction and safety of the building created by them. It is highly decisive to design new structures which are safe and reliable. Added to that, engineer tries hard, so that the structures are economical, architectural appealing and maintain structural performance throughout. Friction based energy dissipation devices has already been proven to be one of the most proficient elucidations in the midst of the reflexive damping systems. The reflexive damping system is introduced to manage the seismic performance of the structure and decreases the damage while the earth quake occurring and post earthquakes. The devices that were developed by for the steel braced frames and concrete panels which is also known to be cost efficient on considering the simplicity of installation and the configuration used for the assembly. This article deals with self centering friction damping braces (SFDBs) which are exposed to maximum seismic response and their performance, during earthquake ground motions [1].

Moment resistant frames (MRFs) and Concentric Braced Frames were the main conventional techniques employed. The above mentioned were the two lateral force resisting systems applied in buildings which are subjected to seismic movements. Moment resisting Frames are those with a rectilinear arrangement of beams and columns, with beams linked to the columns. The frames may be of steel, concrete or masonry. The introduction of suitable type of frames is done based on the soil stability and environmental conditions. This rigid frame action provides the resistance to lateral forces. This resistance is achieved by the developed corresponding bending moment and shear force in the members and joints. A common and efficient method of resisting seismic forces is the concentric braced frame (CBF), which is typically employed in low-rise structures. While comparing both the methods, CBF is more advantageous than MRF which takes load by axial action by bending of beams and columns. The mass of the steel frame is heavy, which subsequently elevate the cost of the project. This can be cut down by replacing CBF over MRF. Considering the major earthquake movements caused in the past, some researchers have focused more on the seismic design approach [2] which dissipates more of energy during the ground motions. These energy dissipaters were found using the passive damping devices. MRFs show high complexity and are highly economical. To cut down this problem, damping forces [3] have been introduced in the system. This maximizes the benefit of withstanding power during seismic actions and controls the bang of the overall structure during and post of the seismic motions. The current study's goal is to examine the impact of SCDF (Self Centering Damage Free) device installation in a steel MRF.

2. Performance based seismic design (PBSD):

Limit State Design is one of the primary developments in seismic analysis over a decade, which is known as performance based engineering [4]. The main sources of earthquake destruction are Ground shaking, Tsunami, failure in the stability and combustion. Performance based Seismic Design shows the architect to how to prevent the damage of the structure from the previous failures. This is obtained by noticing the level of ground shaking and their causes. The level of ground motions have various range and are repaired by performance based engineering. PBSD is applicable to all structures which involves new, existing or in last stage of demolition. PBSD is mainly used to assess the seismic performance and design of the structures. This is done to improvise their overall

performance. The method of optimizing the seismic performance depends on stiffness and ductility [2]. The balance of these parameters checked then and there. Ductility factors vary depending on their seismic design upgrades. These factors are specified separately for seismic force resisting system. It changes according to how well a building performs, the materials utilized, and the relative ductility of the components employed for the successful performance. PBSD is implemented to ensure safety of the people and minimize the cost of the structures.

The major characteristics given consideration to monitor strength of the structures are:

- ❖ Stable foundations
- ❖ Continuous load paths
- ❖ Adequate stiffness and strength
- ❖ regularity
- ❖ redundancy
- ❖ Ductility and Toughness
- ❖ ruggedness

Fig. 1 Performance based design process

3. Resilient-Slip Friction-Joint (RSFJ):

Resilient Slip Friction Joint (RSFJ) is applied on the buildings to increase the seismic performance and reduce the cost thereby assuring the quick reoccupation. RSFJ is a damping device which can produce flag shape hysteresis [5]. Despite the effects of the material used in the structural components, RSFJ is based on friction and offers the necessary seismic performance. RSFJ is used in shear walls, braces with tension, braces with tension and compression and also in moment resisting frames. The inelastic behavior is experienced by the structure where RSFJ is placed, while remaining areas remain elastic. RSFJ brace act in tension and compression, providing self centering and dissipation of energy attached to the steel section conventionally. The braced and the frame are connected by pin, weld or bolt with each other. The telescopic mechanism of steel exhibits the

required stability of the structure. It is applicable to numerous lateral load distribution systems with various configurations. The dampers [6] are used in the joint to provide additional support. The main behavior of the dampers is to check the floor displacement amplitude and inter storey drift. In this study to compare the stability, experiment with and without dampers are carried out.

Fig 2. Self centering materials with dampers

4. Seismic performance evaluation:

The seismic performance is evaluated [7] by placing and non-placing of dampers, which is termed as self centering friction damping brace (SFDB). The absorption of seismic ground vibrations is portrayed in this study. The shape memory alloy used in the dampers is responsible for energy dissipation [8]. It is made of super-elastic nickel-titanium. These wires achieve self centering actions. The prototype is tested by repeated loading of the brace to failure. From these repetitions, it is tested and developed. The results obtained are compared to achieve comparable scaling of linear viscous dampers. The load deformations are monitored. If there is any deformation beyond the limit, secondary fuse is triggered. RSFJ brace provides the self centering twice that of deformation and 1.25 times of the target axial force. To calculate the seismic performance [9] of high storey buildings, nonlinear dynamic history [10] and static push over curve analysis are used.

Fig. 3 The RSFJ's behavior with the secondary fuse is shown by the a-load-deformation curve of clamping.

The results obtained before and after the application of fuse are compared. The joint gets locked if the deformation is 8mm and less than that. Furthermore, it is significant that slip force diminishes when secondary fuse is activated.

Structures are subjected to a nonlinear time history dynamic analysis in order to evaluate their seismic performance. It provides unique detailing of energy dissipation, [11] which paves way for drastic seismic events. Another method adopted was non linear static analysis which is also known as Push over analysis is done to assess how well the structure performs when subjected to lateral loads. It gives the pattern of hinges along with the structural parameters, post earthquake. It is a computer based analysis, and shows various load patterns involved. The hinges formed shows the inability of the structure to withstand loads in beams and columns internally. In the steel bracing, plastic hinges are developed on the bracing rather than column.

4.1. Analytical and Numerical Investigation:

The rotating-RSFJ dissipates seismic energy through the rotational friction sliding of its plates. Friction plates allow the plates to slide against one another with their circular portion. When the external force exceeds the friction barrier between the clamped surfaces, rotational sliding takes place between the surfaces. Stiffness Neutralizer Mechanism (SNM) is applied to cause regulated damage-free elastic buckling. Following the process of SNM, RSFJ activation is initiated. The performance of RSFJ is investigated frequently to check the deviations. The cap plates and middle plates (also known as orange plates) that make up the RSFJ are joined together by high-strength fasteners and prestressed disc springs. The most significant components of the RSFJ are the cap plates and middle plates (orange plates). It has been demonstrated that this damper's axial behavior takes the shape of a flag.

$$P_{slip} = 2n_b P_{pr} \left(\frac{\sin \theta_g + \mu \cos \theta_g}{\cos \theta_g - \mu \sin \theta_g} \right)$$

It is possible to compute the slip moment [12] of the RSFJ, which is caused by symmetric rotations at both ends, by using Eq.

$$M_{in,slip} = n_b P_{pr} b \frac{(\sin \theta_g + \mu \cos \theta_g)}{(\cos \theta_g - \mu \sin \theta_g)}$$

After the unloading phase, a similar calculation can be done for the remaining in-plane moment (M_{res}), but this time with friction in the opposite direction, but this time with friction in the opposite direction, as shown in Eq.

$$M_{in,res} = n_b P_{pr} b \frac{(\sin \theta_g - \mu \cos \theta_g)}{(\cos \theta_g + \mu \sin \theta_g)}$$

5. Design Example:

The frame under consideration is a 10 storied steel braced frame. The steel frame is 37 m long and 6.1 m wide is considered. The rigidity of the frame's members was altered to accommodate the vibrations caused by earthquakes. To accommodate the seismic input employed in this investigation, the stiffness of the frame's members was altered. In the present study, Moment-resisting Braced Frame was considered for the analysis [13]. Moment-resisting braced frame (MRBF) features non-buckling concentric diagonal bracings in each story, the frame and diagonal bracings working together to resist lateral stresses in the structure. The following table lists the characteristics of the employed columns and beams.

Table 1 Properties of beams and columns

Floor Level	Beam	Column	Bracings
	Area (mm ²)		
Story10	6130	10120	1020
Story 9	6130	10120	1020
Story 8	6130	12120	1020
Story 7	6130	12120	1510
Story 6	6130	14330	1510
Story 5	8500	14330	1510
Story 4	8500	18490	1810
Story 3	8500	18490	1810
Story 2	8500	39170	1810
Story 1	8500	39170	1810

The structural parameters which are used in the study are indicated in the table.

Table 2. Structural and site aspects of steel frames

Structural Parameters	MRBF
No of storey's	10
Height of each storey (m)	3.7
Width (m)	6.1
Site Parameters	MRBF
Zone-factor (Z)	0.36
Importance factor(I)	1.2
response reduction factor(r)	5
Type of soil	Medium
Material properties	NMRBF
Grade of steel	FE 250
Yield strength(N/mm ²)	250
Expected yield strength (N/mm ²)	275

Fig.4 Moment resisting braced frame (MRBF) without and with damper

The numerical modeling and analysis [14] of conceptual steel moment resisting braced frame (MRBF) equipped with RSFJs are modeled y using ETABS software. If the design parameters are calibrated correctly, it is possible to model the RSFJ's flag-shaped hysteresis using standard ETABS software.

6. Result:

6.1. Linear Static Analysis of Moment resisting Braced Frame (MRBF)

These are the outcomes of the linear static analysis:

Using the Equivalent Static Approach (ESM) [15], a Forced-Based Design (FBD) technique that is described in, the design force for each of the structural components in this example is determined. If employed here, the Modal Response Spectrum Analysis Method, generally known as RSA, would have been successful.

Table 3 Linear static analyses findings

Floor Level	section	Axial-Stiffness (kN/mm)	Fult (kN)
Story 10	ISLB100	29	34.5
Story 9	ISLB100	29	58.9
Story 8	ISLB100	29	74.8
Story 7	ISLB125	42.5	103.3
Story 6	ISLB125	42.5	105.7
Story 5	ISLB125	42.5	107.6
Story 4	ISLB150	51	118.9
Story 3	ISLB150	51	120.9
Story 2	ISLB150	51	120.7
Story 1	ISLB150	51	137.8

Table 4 Initial configuration of RSFJ braces for Moment resisting braced frame (MRBF)

Story	Brace Code	Section	Initial Stiffness (kN/mm)	F _{slip} (kN)	F _{ult, loading} (kN)	F _{ult, unloading} (kN)	F _{residual} (kN)	Δ _{max} (mm)
Story 10	RSFJ 35	ISLB100	22	17.5	35	45	25	100
Story 9	RSFJ 60	ISLB100	22	30	60	20	12	100
Story 8	RSFJ 80	ISLB100	22	40	80	34	18	100
Story 7	RSFJ 100	ISLB125	29	50	100	41	21	100
Story 6	RSFJ 100	ISLB125	29	62.5	100	41	21	100

Story 5	RSFJ 100	ISLB125	29	62.5	100	41	21	100
Story 4	RSFJ 125	ISLB150	42.5	75	125	58	29.5	100
Story 3	RSFJ 125	ISLB150	42.5	75	125	58	29.5	100
Story 2	RSFJ 125	ISLB150	42.5	75	125	58	29.5	100
Story 1	RSFJ 150	ISLB150	42.5	75	150	45	25	100

6.2. Pushover Analysis

According to the foreign standard, the maximum boundary for buildings [16] vulnerable to ULS earthquakes is 2.5 percent. Additionally, it implies that in the event of an MCE event (with a 1/2500 yearly period of exceedance), this limit may be raised to 3.75 percent.

6.3. Moment resisting Braced Frame (MRBF) Without Dampers

The maximum node displacement amounts to 0.70 m, which is equivalent to a percentage H value of 2%. The Pushover Curve demonstrates that the structure has a Base Shear Capacity that is much higher than the Design Base Shear. On the curve, the points a, b, and c that correspond to 0.5 %, 1.5 %, and 2 % of Displacement correspondingly are indicated. The foundation shear capacity of the building accounts for approximately 37% of its seismic weight.

6.3 a) Pushover curve

Fig.5 Monitored displacement v/s base shear for Moment resisting braced frame without dampers.

6.3 b) Hinge status

Fig. 6 Hinges are formed in the frame at points "a," "b," and "c," correspondingly.

The formation of hinges for earthquakes for a 10-story structure is shown in figure 6 above. To assess hinge development, the frame at points a, b, and c are noted. It is visible that the hinges begin to develop at frame at point ‘a’, ‘b’& ‘c’ and the hinge assembly is now in a dangerous scenario. The structure began to tilt significantly from its initial position and it reaches Collapse prevention threshold in the absence of dampers.

6.4 Moment resisting Braced Frame (MRBF) With Dampers

6.4 a) Pushover curve

The maximum node displacement amounts to 0.745 m, which is equivalent to a percentage H value of 2%. The Pushover Curve demonstrates that the structure has a Base Shear Capacity that is much higher than the Design Base Shear. On the curve, the points a, b, and c that correspond to 0.5 percent, 1.5 percent, and 2 percent of Displacement correspondingly are indicated. About 21.7 percent of the building's seismic weight is used to support its base shear capacity.

Fig.7 Monitored displacement v/s base shear for Moment resisting braced frame with dampers.

6.4 b) Hinge status

Fig.8 No formation of Hinges in the frame at point 'a', 'b' &'c' respectively
It is possible to deduce from the pushover study that the MBrF with dampers are now operating at an immediate operational level.

7. Performance Based Seismic Design

7.1. Moment resisting braced frame (MRBF) with dampers- Design Basis Earthquake(DBE)

Fig.9 Capacity Spectrum for Pushover under DBE

Table 5 Performance point Push- X(DBE)-MRBF with dampers

Magnitude	Result	Magnitude	Result
Base Shear (kN)	86.45	Roof Displacement (m)	0.0272

Spectral Acceleration, S_a (m/s)	0.034	Spectral Displacement, s_d (m)	0.0169
Effective Time Period, T_{eff} (s)	1.491	Effective Damping, β_{eff}	0.057

7.2. Moment resisting braced frame (MRBF) with Dampers-Maximum considered Earthquake (MCE)

Fig.10 Capacity Spectrum for Pushover under MCE

Table 6 Status of performance point Push- X(MCE)-MRBF with dampers

magnitude	Result	Magnitude	Result
Base Shear (kN)	123.12	roof Displacement (m)	0.0585
Spectral Acceleration, S_a (m/s)	0.048	Spectral Displacement, s_d (m)	0.0380
Effective Time Period, T_{eff} (s)	1.998	Effective Damping, β_{eff}	0.1742

The base shear or lateral force (Pushover Curve) associated with the roof displacement at which the structure is operating is well within elastic bounds, and no hinges have yielded.

- After carefully examining all of the curves and tables in the result section, it was determined that the MRBF without dampers was capable of achieving the performance point in the X direction within the elastic limit range for both the designed-based earthquake and the maximum earthquake. Due to the failure of bracings in every story, it was discovered that the MRBF without dampers failed at the last push.
- Within the elastic limit range, the MRBF with dampers was able to reach the performance point in the X direction, for a designed-based earthquake and the inelastic limit range in the case of a maximum considered earthquake, according to the findings of the non linear static

analysis. Even though the structure is approaching the inelastic range, no hinges develop, and the structure remains stable through an earthquake of the highest magnitude.

- The performance point in the MRBF without dampers scenario has a maximum displacement of 0.0853 m, which is less than 1 percent H. As a result, the structure is well within elastic bounds and meets the necessities for operational performance level.
- The performance point in the MRBF with dampers example has a maximum displacement of 0.0585 m, which is less than 1 percent H; as a result, the structure is well within elastic bounds and meets the requirements for operational performance level.

7.3. Base Shears

The base shear for various earthquakes in the MRBF with dampers is decreased by between 5 and 55 percent when compared to the base shear of the MRBF without dampers obtained from the experiment. Due to the RSFJs' ductility and energy dissipation while still retaining its self-centering capabilities, there has been a significant decrease in base shear. From the results, it is evident that the base shear for different earthquakes in the NMRBF with dampers is reduced in the range of 5%-15% when compared with the base shear of NMRBF without dampers. Due to the RSFJs' ductility and energy absorption while still retaining their self-centering capabilities, there has been a significant reduction in base shear.

Fig.11 Comparing the maximum base shears caused by scaled earthquakes.

Figure above shows the base shears. It is apparent that for all of the events, the base shear is under the 120 kN determined using the DBD procedure. No matter how many loading/unloading cycles there are in the system, the internal loads are always contained inside the RSFJ curves. In contrast to systems that are subjected to higher inelastic loads as a result of the members' yielding, the effective modifications can be made by reducing the size of the beams, columns, and other structural elements. Overall, the outcomes of this preliminary numerical modeling clearly showed the RSFJ brace's ability to replace BRBs, viscous dampers, and traditional bracing systems in an effective manner. As traditional braces can be cut and modified to add RSFJs and the jacket to the existing brace body, the RSFJ brace is therefore particularly practical for seismic retrofitting existing buildings.

7.4. Story displacement

Table 7 Elemental level story displacement

Time history	Max Story displacement(mm)	
	Without dampers	With dampers
Altadena	38.37	23.63
El Centro Array 6	76.13	25.08
Corralitos	55.2	5.6
Hollister	48.7	12.62
Century City - Lacc North	39.9	16.93
Lexington Dam	55.29	1.65

Fig.12 comparison of maximum story displacement of MRBF with and without dampers
 The time-history simulations show the largest narrative displacements, and as can be seen from the aforementioned figures, the story displacement of MRBF with RSFJ dampers is decreased by 30 to 97% compared to MRBF without dampers.

7.5. Story Drift

A common core acceptance criterion that is utilised in numerous standards and recommendations is story drifts. The easiest way to assess story drift is to simply calculate the distance between two stories, normalised by their height (also known as the drift ratio).

Table 8 Elemental Level Storey Drift without dampers

Story	Max drift							limit (0.004xH)
	ALTADE NA	EL CENTRO ARRAY 6	CORRALITOS	HOLLISTER	CENTUR Y CITY - LACC NORTH	LEXINGTO NDAM	LUCERNE VALLEY	
Story10	0.000774	0.001344	0.000969	0.001147	0.000819	0.001183	0.0005	0.148
Story9	0.001095	0.001881	0.001328	0.001611	0.001252	0.001642	0.000867	0.148
Story8	0.000937	0.002009	0.001134	0.001743	0.001425	0.001547	0.001035	0.148
Story7	0.001306	0.002116	0.00174	0.001476	0.001317	0.001656	0.000952	0.148
Story6	0.0011	0.001892	0.001662	0.0012	0.001041	0.001376	0.000763	0.148
Story5	0.00087	0.001785	0.001544	0.001054	0.000879	0.001204	0.000657	0.148
Story4	0.000846	0.00188	0.001631	0.001036	0.000855	0.001225	0.000664	0.148
Story3	0.001001	0.00224	0.001846	0.001174	0.000954	0.001474	0.000768	0.148
Story2	0.001143	0.002545	0.001757	0.001298	0.001053	0.001702	0.000866	0.148
Story1	0.001378	0.002903	0.001399	0.001465	0.00123	0.001962	0.001032	0.148

Table 9 Elemental Level Storey Drift with dampers

Story	Max drift							limit (0.004xH)
	ALTADE NA	EL CENTRO ARRAY 6	CORRALITOS	HOLLISTER	CENTUR Y CITY - LACC NORTH	LEXINGTO NDAM	LUCERNE VALLEY	
Story10	0.000444	0.000255	5.40E-05	0.000315	0.00033	8.80E-05	0.000272	0.148
Story9	0.000578	0.000349	7.70E-05	0.000371	0.00043	8.90E-05	0.000362	0.148
Story8	0.000678	0.000466	9.50E-05	0.000413	0.000492	9.10E-05	0.00043	0.148
Story7	0.000701	0.000596	0.000129	0.000373	0.000498	5.80E-05	0.000456	0.148
Story6	0.000707	0.000645	0.000146	0.000359	0.000494	4.60E-05	0.000464	0.148
Story5	0.00069	0.000613	0.000175	0.000314	0.000483	1.50E-05	0.000462	0.148
Story4	0.000675	0.000676	0.00019	0.000311	0.000474	1.20E-05	0.000454	0.148
Story3	0.000677	0.000844	0.000222	0.000309	0.000485	3.00E-06	0.000458	0.148
Story2	0.00063	0.001089	0.000207	0.000331	0.000447	3.00E-05	0.000415	0.148
Story1	0.000662	0.001282	0.000233	0.000362	0.000479	3.30E-05	0.000441	0.148

Fig.13 Utmost Inter- storey drift – MRBF without dampers.

Fig.14 Maximum inter story drift – MRBF with RSFJ dampers.

As can be observed from the aforementioned graphs, the biggest inter-story drifts were found across the time-history simulations. The seven-time historical data shows that the narrative drift of MRBF with RSFJ dampers is reduced in the range of 20 to 98 percent when compared to the story drift of MRBF without dampers.

7.6. Story Acceleration

Fig.15 Acceleration at the top floors for different considered earthquakes.

The acceleration for the MRBF with dampers decreased to 24-55 percent as compared to the MRBF without dampers is clearly shown in the above graph.

8. Conclusion

The conclusion drawn from the study helps the future engineer to construct the structures with high performance and stability during ground motions.

Based on the outcomes of the analysis, RSFJ can be utilized to lessen the reaction of the structure. The pushover analysis results show that MRBF began to tilt significantly from its initial position and it reaches Collapse prevention threshold in the absence of RSFJ. The time history analysis gives a percentage of 30% 95% of reduction in storey displacement for MRBF with RSFJ. The nonlinear time history analysis concludes that the structure began to tilt significantly from its initial position after 15 seconds, and the hinge assembly is in a dangerous scenario with the absence of RSFJ. The study shows that there is a considerable base shear reduction. The RSFJs' capacity to dissipate energy and give ductility while yet retaining self-centering is what causes the base shear to be reduced. In the plane steel frame, the maximum storey drifts are well reduced by the introduction of the RSFJ. It can be seen that for all of the ULS and MCE events, the peak roof responses are considerably below the FEMA 356 limits which confirms the efficiency of this system. In other words, the RSFJ bracing system offers predictable behavior with no post-event issues. The present study suggests that the RSFJ can effectively disperse the seismic energy during an earthquake without causing any harm to the beam, columns, connection, or joints and can also stop the system's residual drift. From all the analyses, we can conclude that self centering friction damper's usage at joints in case of conventional ductility based design; confer superlative output on the design of earthquake occurrence structures.

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